

Comparison of Various Intrathecal Clonidine Doses as an Adjuvant to Bupivacaine for Lower Limb Surgeries: A Prospective Observational Study

Ankit Verma¹, Neha Pandey², Amit Kumar³

¹PG Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology & Critical Care, MGM Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, India

²PG Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology, MGM Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology, MGM Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Amit Kumar

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Abstract:

Background: This prospective observational study evaluated the effect of varying doses of intrathecal clonidine as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in patients undergoing lower limb surgeries.

Methods: A total of 150 patients were randomly assigned to receive low (30 mcg), moderate (45 mcg), or high (60 mcg) doses of clonidine alongside 15 mg of hyperbaric bupivacaine. The primary outcomes measured included the onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade, duration of postoperative analgesia, and incidence of side effects.

Results: Results indicated that higher doses of clonidine significantly expedited the onset of sensory block and prolonged both sensory and motor blockade durations. However, increased dosages were also associated with a higher incidence of adverse effects, particularly hypotension and sedation. Moderate doses (45 mcg) provided an optimal balance between effective analgesia and reduced side effects.

Conclusion: This study suggests that moderate doses of intrathecal clonidine may serve as a standard practice in spinal anesthesia for lower limb surgeries. Careful dose selection is essential for enhancing patient outcomes while minimizing risks associated with regional anesthesia.

Keywords: Clonidine, Bupivacaine, Spinal Anesthesia, Lower Limb Surgery.

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Introduction

Intrathecal anesthesia, frequently employed for lower limb surgeries, benefits from the addition of adjuvants to enhance the effects of local anesthetics like bupivacaine. Bupivacaine, a long-acting local anesthetic, provides effective sensory and motor blockade, but its duration may be insufficient for longer surgeries or prolonged postoperative analgesia. Clonidine, an alpha-2 adrenergic agonist, has shown promise as an adjuvant to bupivacaine, enhancing and extending its analgesic effects through spinal receptor modulation. Its application in intrathecal anesthesia is of interest due to its ability to reduce intraoperative anesthetic requirements, improve hemodynamic stability, and reduce postoperative opioid consumption, thus improving overall patient outcomes [1,2].

Recent studies have aimed to optimize clonidine dosing to maximize these benefits while minimizing side effects. For example, a 2022 study compared low (15–30 mcg) and moderate (45–60 mcg) doses of intrathecal clonidine combined with

bupivacaine for lower limb surgeries. It was found that low doses provided sufficient analgesia and hemodynamic stability with fewer incidences of hypotension and sedation compared to higher doses, which, while extending sensory and motor blockade, increased the likelihood of side effects like bradycardia and excessive sedation (Sharma et al., 2022) [3].

Another recent meta-analysis evaluated the efficacy and safety profiles of various clonidine doses in spinal anesthesia, concluding that moderate doses (30–50 mcg) offer a balanced analgesic effect with acceptable safety margins in adult patients undergoing lower extremity surgeries (Wang et al., 2021) [4]. These studies indicate a trend toward using lower doses of clonidine to achieve optimal patient outcomes, with careful monitoring to avoid adverse hemodynamic events. This area of research continues to evolve, as clinicians seek to establish an ideal intrathecal clonidine dose that offers maximum analgesic duration and minimal side

effects for safer, more effective lower limb surgery outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective observational study compared intrathecal clonidine dosages as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in lower limb surgery patients. MGM Medical College & LSK Hospital, Kishanganj, Bihar, hosted the 13-month study from June 2023 to July 2024. Before starting the study, the institutional ethics committee approved it, and all patients provided written informed consent.

Study Population: A total of 150 patients scheduled for lower limb surgeries under spinal anesthesia were included in the study. Patients were selected based on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 18 to 55 years.
- American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I and II.
- Patients undergoing elective lower limb surgeries.
- Patients willing to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with known allergy to clonidine or bupivacaine.
- Patients with contraindications to spinal anesthesia (e.g., coagulopathy, infection at the injection site, severe hypovolemia).
- Patients with significant cardiovascular, renal, hepatic, or neurological disorders.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients with a history of substance abuse or chronic opioid use.

Group Allocation: Although the study is observational, patients were divided into three groups on the basis of intrathecal clonidine dose, which was established by clinical judgment and patient state. Bupivacaine (0.5% hyperbaric) was given to all groups, although clonidine doses varied:

- **Group A (Low Dose Clonidine):** 30 mcg of clonidine + 15 mg of bupivacaine.
- **Group B (Moderate Dose Clonidine):** 45 mcg of clonidine + 15 mg of bupivacaine.
- **Group C (High Dose Clonidine):** 60 mcg of clonidine + 15 mg of bupivacaine.

Procedure: All patients underwent a medical history, physical examination, and laboratory tests before surgery. Patients received 0.2 mg/kg oral alprazolam the night before surgery. Upon entering

the surgery room, non-invasive blood pressure, pulse oximetry, and ECG monitoring began. Baseline heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation were assessed. Patients received spinal anesthesia in either the sitting or lateral decubitus position. A 25-gauge Quincke spinal needle was used to access the L3-L4 or L4-L5 interspace aseptically. Upon establishing CSF flow, the prescribed dosage of clonidine and 15 mg of hyperbaric bupivacaine (0.5%) were injected intrathecally. Afterward, patients were positioned supine. Intraoperative monitoring included continuous heart rate, blood pressure, respiration, and oxygen saturation. Hemodynamic parameters were recorded every 5 minutes for 30 minutes, then every 15 minutes until surgery concluded.

Data Collection: Data included the onset of sensory blockade (from injection to T10 sensory level using a pinprick test) and motor blockade (from injection to Bromage score of 3). Sensory blockade duration was monitored from injection to sensory regression to S1, while motor blockade was assessed from injection to a Bromage score of 0 (full motor function recovery). Hemodynamic parameters, including heart rate and blood pressure, were measured at baseline, every 5 minutes for 30 minutes, and then every 15 minutes afterward. The duration of postoperative analgesia was recorded from the time of intrathecal injection to the first request for rescue analgesia (VAS score > 4). Any adverse events such as hypotension (MAP <65 mmHg), bradycardia (HR <50 beats/min), nausea, vomiting, drowsiness, respiratory depression, and surgical complications such as urinary retention or neurological impairments were also documented.

Statistical Analysis: Statistics were analyzed using SPSS 25.0. Continuous variables (e.g., sensory and motor blockade duration, postoperative analgesia duration) were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) or Student's t-test, where appropriate. Categorical variables, such as the incidence of side effects, were compared using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value <0.05.

Results

The study included 150 patients who were divided into three groups based on intrathecal clonidine dosage. Groups A, B, and C received low (30 mcg), moderate (45 mcg), and high (60 mcg) doses of clonidine, respectively, in addition to 15 mg of hyperbaric bupivacaine. The demographic characteristics, sensory and motor block characteristics, duration of analgesia, and incidence of side effects were recorded and analyzed across the groups.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Group A (30 mcg)	Group B (45 mcg)	Group C (60 mcg)	p-value
Number of Patients	50	50	50	-
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	40.5 $\pm$ 8.2	41.1 $\pm$ 7.9	42.0 $\pm$ 8.0	0.51
ASA I / II (%)	60 / 40	58 / 42	62 / 38	0.63
Male/Female Ratio	28/22	27/23	30/20	0.44

Table 2: Comparison of Sensory and Motor Block Characteristics

Parameter	Group A (30 mcg)	Group B (45 mcg)	Group C (60 mcg)	p-value
Onset of Sensory Block (min)	4.5 $\pm$ 1.0	4.2 $\pm$ 0.9	3.8 $\pm$ 0.7	0.02*
Onset of Motor Block (min)	6.0 $\pm$ 1.1	5.8 $\pm$ 1.0	5.5 $\pm$ 0.9	0.08
Duration of Sensory Block (min)	150 $\pm$ 15	165 $\pm$ 18	180 $\pm$ 20	<0.01*
Duration of Motor Block (min)	130 $\pm$ 12	150 $\pm$ 15	165 $\pm$ 18	<0.01*
Duration of Analgesia (min)	300 $\pm$ 30	350 $\pm$ 35	400 $\pm$ 40	<0.01*

*p-value <0.05 is considered statistically significant.

Table 3: Incidence of Side Effects

Side Effect	Group A (30 mcg)	Group B (45 mcg)	Group C (60 mcg)	p-value
Hypotension (%)	12%	18%	26%	0.03*
Bradycardia (%)	10%	15%	20%	0.04*
Nausea (%)	8%	10%	14%	0.15
Drowsiness (%)	6%	10%	18%	0.02*
Respiratory Depression (%)	2%	4%	6%	0.28

Summary of Findings:

- **Sensory and Motor Block Characteristics:** Group C (60 mcg) showed the fastest onset of sensory block and the longest duration of both sensory and motor block compared to Groups A and B. However, Group C also had a significantly higher incidence of hypotension, bradycardia, and drowsiness.
- **Analgesia Duration:** The duration of analgesia was significantly longer in Group C, followed by Group B, and shortest in Group A.
- **Side Effects:** Higher clonidine doses were associated with an increased incidence of side effects. Group C had a notably higher frequency of hypotension and drowsiness than Groups A and B.

In conclusion, moderate doses of clonidine (45 mcg) provided a favorable balance between effective analgesia duration and a lower incidence of side effects, while the higher dose (60 mcg) offered prolonged analgesia but at an increased risk of adverse events

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of various doses of intrathecal clonidine as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in patients undergoing lower limb surgeries. Our findings demonstrated that increasing the dosage of clonidine significantly influenced both the onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade, as well as the duration of postoperative analgesia. Specifically, patients in

Group C (60 mcg of clonidine) experienced a quicker onset of sensory block and a longer duration of both sensory and motor blocks compared to Groups A (30 mcg) and B (45 mcg). However, this higher dosage was associated with an increased incidence of adverse effects, including hypotension and sedation [5,6].

These results are consistent with recent studies exploring the role of clonidine in regional anesthesia. For instance, a systematic review by Dyer et al. (2023) [7] confirmed that lower doses of intrathecal clonidine (20-40 mcg) can provide effective analgesia while minimizing side effects. Their findings highlighted that high dose, although beneficial for extending the duration of analgesia, were linked to a higher frequency of hypotension and bradycardia, aligning with our study's observations.

Similarly, a study by Choi et al. (2021) [8] investigated the effects of intrathecal clonidine on sensory and motor blockade during lower limb surgeries and found that patients receiving 45 mcg exhibited a significant increase in analgesia duration compared to those receiving lower doses. This study also noted that while higher doses did prolong analgesia, they resulted in more pronounced side effects, reaffirming the importance of careful dosage selection.

The implications of our study highlight the necessity of finding an optimal balance between effective analgesia and minimizing adverse effects. Using moderate doses of clonidine could potentially reduce the requirement for additional

analgesics, thereby decreasing the risk of opioid-related side effects and improving recovery times [9]. Future research should focus on further refining the dosing strategies for clonidine as an adjuvant in various surgical contexts. Investigating the effects of clonidine in conjunction with other adjuvants, such as dexmedetomidine or magnesium sulfate, may yield synergistic benefits that enhance analgesia while maintaining a favorable side effect profile. Additionally, exploring the role of patient-specific factors, including genetics and comorbidities, could provide insights into optimizing anesthetic techniques tailored to individual patients [10,11].

Furthermore, multicenter randomized controlled trials with larger sample sizes will be crucial for establishing comprehensive guidelines for the use of intrathecal clonidine across diverse surgical populations. Such studies can contribute to the development of evidence-based practices that enhance patient safety and comfort during and after surgery [12]. The study reinforces the effect of intrathecal clonidine as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in lower limb surgeries, emphasizing the need for optimal dosage selection to balance analgesia with safety. As research in this area continues to evolve, it holds the promise of improving patient outcomes and advancing the field of regional anesthesia.

Conclusion

This study shows that intrathecal clonidine is an effective adjuvant to bupivacaine for lower limb procedures, prolonging sensory and motor blocking and postoperative analgesia. Higher doses increase side effects, including haemodynamic instability. A dose of 45 mcg clonidine appears to balance sustained analgesia with low side effects, making it a feasible alternative for improving spinal anaesthesia effect in clinical practice.

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